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Improving the Performance of Machine Learning Models by Augmenting Composite Coating Bath Design Data Using a Gaussian Noise-Based Data Augmentation Method

Emel Akyürek¹, Özer Uygun², Fatih Taşkın², Enes Furkan Erkan², Harun Gül³, Mehmet Uysal⁴,
Abdullah Hulusi Kökçam², Hasan Algül⁴, Sezer Tan⁴, Ahmet Alp⁴

¹ Sakarya University of Applied Sciences, Arifiye Vocational School, Sakarya, Türkiye
emel@subu.edu.tr

² Sakarya University, Department of Industrial Engineering, Sakarya, Türkiye
ouygun@sakarya.edu.tr, mftaskin@sakarya.edu.tr, eneserkan@sakarya.edu.tr, akokcam@sakarya.edu.tr

³ Sakarya University of Applied Sciences, Dept. of Metallurgical and Materials Eng., Sakarya, Türkiye
harungul@subu.edu.tr

⁴ Sakarya University, Dept. of Metallurgical and Materials Eng., Sakarya, Türkiye
mehmetu@sakarya.edu.tr, halgul@sakarya.edu.tr, sezertan@sakarya.edu.tr, alp@sakarya.edu.tr

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a novel approach based on data augmentation through the addition of Gaussian noise to limited experimental data was employed to support the inverse optimization of bath parameters for achieving the targeted properties of composite coatings, and the impact of this approach on the performance of machine learning (ML) models was investigated. The study began with the initial limited experimental data obtained in accordance with the Taguchi experimental design. Before proceeding with the data augmentation process, the conformity of the dataset's features to a normal distribution was analyzed and verified. Subsequently, Gaussian noise, considered a natural representation of experimental measurement deviations, was added to the original dataset, significantly expanding its size. Furthermore, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and two-way interaction plots were employed to identify the key factors affecting coating properties and their interactions. The augmented dataset, along with the original raw dataset, was then used to train and test various ML models. Model performance was evaluated in terms of predictive accuracy and robustness. The successful predictive performance achieved through data augmentation and ML models provides a foundation for future inverse optimization of bath parameters in line with the targeted coating properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

In materials science, improving corrosion resistance, wear properties, and other surface characteristics is among the key strategies for the practical applications of metals in various industries. In this context, the electroless coating method stands out as an effective and important technique for producing homogeneous coatings [1]. Electroless nickel-phosphorus (Ni-P) coatings have long been extensively studied and utilized due to their superior properties such as corrosion resistance, wear resistance, and high hardness [2]. Electroless nickel-boron (Ni-B) coatings, on the other hand, have attracted attention for their outstanding properties since 1989 [1]. Compared to Ni-P coatings, Ni-B coatings possess higher mechanical properties and have become indispensable in many applications thanks to their excellent corrosion resistance, high wear resistance, high hardness, and good oxidation resistance [1], [3]. Furthermore, to further enhance the properties of these coatings, electroless composite coatings have been developed by incorporating various nanoparticles (e.g., SiC, B₄C, Al₂O₃, CeO₂, TiO₂) [1].

In materials science, machine learning (ML) models are widely employed to accelerate research in the field and to reduce the high cost and long duration associated with traditional trial-and-error methods [4].

In materials science, ML is employed in various domains such as predicting material properties, constructing atomic potentials, identifying functional candidates, analyzing complex reaction networks, and guiding experimental design [5]. It is also applied in tasks such as phase and hardness prediction of high-entropy alloys (HEAs) [6].

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) [7], [8], Decision Trees [9], and Multiple Linear Regression [10] are machine learning models used for prediction tasks in various engineering applications.

ML models require large amounts of training data [11]. Compared to other fields, materials data typically tend to be smaller in quantity and sometimes more diverse [5]. The limited amount of data directly affects the predictive accuracy of ML models and can lead to issues such as overfitting [12]. To address these limitations, data augmentation techniques have emerged as an effective way to increase the size and quality of the training dataset by modifying or synthesizing existing data [13], [14].

In recent years, various data augmentation methods have gained prominence in the literature for their applications across different disciplines [15]. Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN)-based augmentation methods have achieved high accuracy in areas such as fault diagnosis [16], corrosion growth prediction [17], and time-series modeling; however, they have offered limited reliability due to training instability [18]. Similarly, generative models such as Variational Autoencoders (VAE) produce stable results in data generation [12], [14] but present certain limitations in terms of maintaining sample diversity and realism, in the study by Žvirblis et al. (2024) [14], a significant decrease in classification accuracy was observed for signals generated by a Time VAE variational autoencoder. Possible reasons for this include the dataset's unsuitability for variational autoencoders or the improper selection of parameters. The failure of the generated signals to capture the noise and fine details of the original signal may have confused the neural network, resulting in poor performance.

Data augmentation through the addition of Gaussian noise has attracted attention due to both its ease of implementation [16] and its advantages in statistical control [6]. Ye et al. (2023) [6] demonstrated that data augmented with Gaussian noise significantly improved accuracy rates ($R^2 = 0.954$) in phase classification and hardness regression tasks for high-entropy alloys. Consistent with Zhang and Ling's (2018) [5] Crude Estimation of Property (CEP) strategy, Gaussian-based augmentation methods also contribute to extracting statistical relationships from the limited number of reliable existing data. The use of Gaussian noise not only enhances performance but also models the natural variances of physical systems [6].

Although synthetic data generation using generative deep learning models such as GANs and VAEs has been successfully applied, these methods often face challenges such as high computational requirements and mode collapse [15], [18]. Alternatively, Gaussian (normal) noise-based data augmentation offers a low-cost and physically consistent approach by mimicking measurement deviations [6], [16].

In this study, considering the methods used and the results obtained in previous studies on synthetic data generation, Gaussian noise-based data augmentation—a low-cost and controlled technique—was preferred; composite coating data augmented using this method were successfully applied in machine learning regression models.

The aim of this study is to enhance the predictive performance of ML models in composite coatings by employing a data augmentation method based on Gaussian noise, thereby laying the groundwork for the future inverse optimization of bath parameters.

2 METHODOLOGY

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2.1 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Interaction Analysis

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) identifies which material properties or process parameters have a statistically significant effect on the results and reveals the impact of interactions between different factors on material performance [19]. To statistically examine the effects of input parameters on the dependent variables in the dataset (e.g., coating thickness, hardness, etc.), ANOVA was applied. In addition, two-way interaction plots were utilized to visually assess the combined effects of two factors on the output. These analyses were repeated for both the raw and noise-augmented datasets.

2.2 Dataset and Gaussian (Normal) Noise-Based Data Augmentation

The Ni-B-B₄C composite coating data generated using the Taguchi experimental design include input variables such as heat treatment, boron carbide (B₄C) concentration, and surfactant, as well as output variables such as coating thickness, hardness, wear resistance, and corrosion resistance. The dataset consists of 18 observations with two replications per output. Before proceeding to the data augmentation phase, the distribution characteristics of the raw data were analysed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. The Shapiro–Wilk test is one of the methods used to assess the normality of continuous data. It is particularly suitable for small sample sizes ($n < 50$), but can also be applied to larger datasets. In this test, the null hypothesis (H_0) assumes that the data come from a normally distributed population. When the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the data are interpreted as normally distributed [20].

Gaussian noise is a common type of noise, defined as a random number whose probability density function follows a Gaussian distribution. The noise value is closely related to the standard deviation (σ); as σ increases, the data exhibits a wider spread. By adding Gaussian noise, the raw data

is slightly modified and becomes noisy data [6]. In this study, Gaussian noise was added to the dataset, generating two noisy samples for each data point and expanding the dataset from 18 to 54 observations. The Gaussian noise level used in the study was determined based on a specific proportion of the standard deviations (approximately one-thirtieth), taking into account the distribution characteristics of the output variables.

2.3 Machine Learning Models

The machine learning models employed in this study include Decision Tree Regressor, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models. Decision tree-based algorithms have been successfully applied to a wide range of tasks, including classification, regression, and feature selection. The core principle of these algorithms is to recursively split the dataset into subsets based on the values of different features and to continue this process until a stopping criterion is met - typically when the nodes become pure (i.e., all data points in the node belong to the same class) or the tree reaches a predefined depth. The resulting structure is a tree-like graph, where the terminal points of the tree, called leaves or terminal nodes, represent the predicted outcomes or class labels [21]. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) is a statistical technique used to predict the outcome of a response (dependent) variable using multiple explanatory (independent) variables. The aim of MLR is to model the linear relationship between the independent variables (x) and the dependent variable (y) [22]. An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is known as an adaptive information processing system composed of numerous interconnected processing units (neurons). ANN has an unprogrammed data processing architecture and performs parallel/distributed information processing through network transformations [23].

In this study, the data preprocessing stage involved normalizing the data and encoding categorical variables. For the performance evaluation of the machine learning models, the Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and five-fold cross-validation (average R^2) were employed. The decision to apply cross-validation was based on the study by Naser and Amir H. (2023) [24], who emphasized that while various performance metrics are used in engineering applications of machine learning (ML), they cannot fully prevent common issues such as overfitting and bias. Therefore, they recommend incorporating different degrees of cross-validation to enhance the generalizability and reliability of ML-based analyses. A lower RMSE value indicates better model performance [18], while an R^2 value close to 1 signifies stronger model fitting performance [17]. The coding for training and evaluating the models was carried out in Python using the relevant libraries within the Google Colab environment.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Findings on Gaussian (Normal) Noise-Based Data Augmentation

Before proceeding with the data augmentation process, since the number of data points was less than 50, the distribution characteristics of the variables were analyzed using the Shapiro–Wilk test, implemented in Python. For the output variable *Coating Thickness*, the test results were as follows: Shapiro–Wilk Test: Statistic = 0.9221, p-value = 0.1411, indicating that the data follow a normal distribution (H_0 not rejected). In Figure 1, the Q–Q (Quantile–Quantile) plot also shows that the data align linearly. Similar results were obtained for the other variables as well.

Figure 1: Q–Q plot for the coating thickness of the Ni-B-B₄C composite coating

After confirming that the dataset followed a normal distribution, Gaussian noise—adjusted according to the standard deviation of the data—was added to the raw dataset, tripling the number of data points and increasing data diversity. In this study, particular care was taken to conduct statistical normality checks during the process of determining the noise level and to ensure that the synthetic data remained within physical limits.

3.2 ANOVA Findings

The parameters affecting the coating thickness response variable were analyzed using ANOVA, and as shown in Table 1, the adjusted R^2 value was found to be 98.7%. This indicates that the factors included in the model explain 98.71% of the variability in the dependent variable (coating thickness) and that the model is highly robust. Since the p-values for surfactant and B₄C concentration were below 0.05, these factors were found to have a statistically significant effect on coating thickness, whereas the effect of heat treatment, with a p-value above 0.05, was statistically insignificant. The interaction plots demonstrated that the effect of parameters on the output varied for certain combinations; for example, the presence or absence of heat treatment had no significant influence on coating thickness, as evidenced by the parallelism of the interaction curves. When the surfactant was SDS and the B₄C concentration was 10, the coating thickness increased (see Fig. 2).

Table 1 ANOVA results for Ni-B-B₄C composite coating thickness (for raw data)

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution (%)	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Heat Treatment	1	0,1	0,4	0,1	0,1	5,3	0,08
Surfactant	2	13,7	53,26	13,7	6,85	353,42	0
B ₄ C concentration	2	10,3	40,01	10,3	5,15	265,49	0
Heat Treatment : Surfactant	2	0,08	0,3	0,08	0,04	2	0,25
Heat Treatment : B ₄ C concentration	2	0,16	0,61	0,16	0,08	4,02	0,11
Surfactant : B ₄ C concentration	4	1,32	5,12	1,32	0,33	16,97	0,01
Residual	4	0,08	0,3	0,08	0,02		
Output	R-sq (%)	R-sq(adj) (%)					
Coating Thickness __mm__	99,698578	98,7189574					

a)

b)

c)

Figure 2: a) Composite Coating Thickness – Heat Treatment & Surfactant Interaction Plot (left: raw data, right: noise-augmented data) b) Composite Coating Thickness – Heat Treatment & B4C Concentration Interaction Plot c) Composite Coating Thickness – Surfactant & B4C Concentration Interaction Plot (left: raw data, right: noise-augmented data)

As shown in Table 2, the ANOVA analyses performed after data augmentation yielded similar p-values and contribution rates, indicating that the variance structure was preserved in the dataset obtained after augmentation. As seen in Figure 2, the direction of the interaction plots and the variance distribution for the expanded dataset are also highly consistent with those of the raw data. The ANOVA results and interaction plots obtained for other output variables likewise demonstrated that the variance structure was preserved following the data augmentation process.

Table 2 ANOVA results for Ni-B-B4C composite coating thickness (for noise-augmented data)

Source	DF	Seq SS	Contribution (%)	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Heat Treatment	1	0,23	0,44	0,23	0,23	45,88	0
Surfactant (g/L)	2	28,23	54,27	28,23	14,12	2814,4	0
B4C concentration	2	20,35	39,11	20,35	10,17	2028,05	0
Heat Treatment : Surfactant	2	0,2	0,38	0,2	0,1	19,55	0
Heat Treatment : B4C concentration	2	0,29	0,56	0,29	0,14	28,78	0
Surfactant : B4C concentration	4	2,62	5,03	2,62	0,65	130,39	0
Residual	22	0,11	0,21	0,11	0,01		
Output	R-sq (%)	R-sq(adj) (%)					
Coating Thickness __mm_	99,78787	99,66252					

3.3 Performance Analysis of Machine Learning Models

Machine learning (ML) models trained on the expanded dataset exhibited higher accuracy (R^2) and lower error rates (RMSE) compared to those trained on the raw dataset. Table 3 presents the performance results of the machine learning models for the coating thickness output variable. Analyses conducted on the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model revealed that the Gaussian noise-based data augmentation method provided a substantial improvement in performance metrics. The average R^2 value obtained with the raw dataset was 0.526, whereas this value increased to 0.998 with the expanded dataset. Similarly, the RMSE value decreased from 0.268 to 0.025, indicating a significant reduction in prediction error. These results demonstrate that the data augmentation approach considerably enhanced the prediction accuracy of the ANN model. Similar improvements were observed for the other output variables as well.

Table 3 Comparison of Performance Metrics of ML Models for the Ni-B-B4C Composite Coating Thickness Using the Raw Dataset and the Gaussian Noise-Augmented Expanded Dataset

Model	R^2 (Raw)	R^2 (Raw + Gaussian Noise)	RMSE (Raw)	RMSE (Raw + Gaussian Noise)	Mean R^2 (Raw)	Mean R^2 (Raw + Gaussian Noise)
Decision Tree	-0,033	0,997	0,284	0,027	0,826	0,999
Multiple Linear Regression	-0,346	0,77	0,324	0,253	0,828	0,926
ANN	0,079	0,998	0,268	0,025	0,526	0,998

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The dataset of Ni-B-B4C composite coatings, obtained from experiments conducted in accordance with the Taguchi experimental design, consists of 18 observations. To enhance the performance of machine learning models, the distribution characteristics of the raw data were first examined using the Shapiro–Wilk test prior to data augmentation, and the results indicated compliance with a normal distribution. Subsequently, Gaussian noise scaled to a specific proportion of the data's standard deviation ($\text{std}/30$) was added to expand the dataset, resulting in notable improvements in performance metrics (increase in R^2 , decrease in RMSE). For example, in the multiple linear regression model, the average R^2 value increased from 0.828 in the raw dataset to 0.926 in the expanded dataset, while the RMSE value decreased from 0.324 to 0.253. Similarly, for the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model, the average R^2 value rose from 0.526 to 0.998, and the RMSE value dropped from 0.268 to 0.025.

The findings obtained are methodologically and substantively consistent with the study by Žvirblis et al. (2024) [14], which applied data augmentation by adding Gaussian noise at different proportions of the data standard deviation (std/90, std/30) and reported significant improvements in model accuracy. The ANOVA analyses conducted revealed that the noise-augmented datasets preserved their statistical integrity and exhibited characteristics consistent with the original dataset.

In future studies, inverse optimization of bath parameters will be performed using the developed ML models to achieve the desired coating properties, and the generalizability of the method will be tested on different noise distributions and coating systems.

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